
Horizontal and vertical mobilisation of microplastics in agricultural soils: run-off and infiltration experiments

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Abstract

Mulching films are commonly used in agriculture to improve crop growth and yield, and to decrease the use of irrigation water and phytosanitary products. Nevertheless, they have been described as one of the most relevant sources of microplastics (MPs) in agricultural soils. The presence of MPs in soil may disrupt soil physical structure, affect water and nutrient retention, and compromise the health of plants and soil organisms. Due to the impact of conventional plastics on soil pollution, the use of biodegradable mulching films has been proposed as an alternative. However, the transport and fate of the particles resulting from their degradation in soils remain largely unknown. This study aims to evaluate the mobilisation of biodegradable MPs through surface runoff and infiltration through the soil towards groundwater. Additionally, the experiment explores the effect of crops on MP mobility. Six modified Pinson collectors (2x1x0.5 m) with a slope of 5° were filled with natural soil. The uppermost 4 cm were mixed with polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) fragments from biodegradable mulching films at 0.5 wt%. Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) was planted in three collectors whereas the rest were left with bare soil. Samples of run-off water from rainfall and irrigation, water infiltrating at 10 and 30 cm depth, and soil interstitial water were periodically collected. PBAT fragments were identified with a Fourier Transform Infrared microscope (μ FTIR; Bruker Lumos II FPA) and data analysis was performed in a simple software by using an in-house reference spectra database. After harvesting, soil samples from all collectors were retrieved at different depths for analysing MP content. Samples collected from all matrices are currently being analysed however preliminary data confirms the presence of MPs in soil at 10 cm depth, suggesting their migration from the surface. Final results will provide insights into MP transport in a simulated agricultural scenario.

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